

TO STUDY THE RELATIONSHIP OF TNF α (G-308A) GENE POLYMORPHISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF APLASTIC ANEMIA

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Summary

Purpose of the study. To analyze the functional significance of polymorphism of the proinflammatory cytokine TNF α (G-308A) gene in the development of aplastic anemia.

Methods. Detection of polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (rs1800629) in 86 patients with AA and 98 healthy ones using polymerase chain reaction in standard mode with visualization of electrophoresis products on a programmable thermal cycler "Rotor Gene Q" (Quagen, Germany).

In groups of patients with AA and healthy, a molecular genetic analysis was performed with DNA isolation from peripheral blood using a set of reagents "AmpliPrime RIBOT-prep" (Russia) and detection of TNF α genetic polymorphism (rs1800629) using test systems "Litech, NPF LLC" (Russia). The amplification process was reproduced on the GeneAmp PCR-system 2720 thermal cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA). The amplified products were subjected to electrophoresis in 2% agarose gel to study band patterns using ethidium bromide. Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the OpenEpi – 2009 software package (Version 2.3).

Conclusions. Genetic polymorphism TNF α (rs1800629) is not associated with the risk of developing aplastic anemia.

Key words: Tumor necrosis factor- α TNF α (rs1800629), single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP), autoimmune disease, proinflammatory cytokine.

Introduction. Tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) is a pro-inflammatory cytokine produced by various immune cells, including antigen-stimulated T cells, lymphocytes and NK cells [2,4,5]. Its effect is to limit concomitant damage to

host cells and tissues during an inflammatory reaction and to maintain a balance between inflammatory and anti-inflammatory reactions [1,9,11].

TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor- α) is important for the normal functioning of the body, but is also involved in some disease mechanisms, including sepsis, diabetes mellitus, and cancer [8,10].

Recent studies have shown that defective functioning of regulatory T cells leads to increased production of interferon gamma (IFN- γ) and tissue necrosis factor (TNF- α), causing damage to stem cells, which leads to bone marrow aplasia [3,6,7,12].

To determine the distribution of SNP loci of the TNF α polymorphic gene (G-308A) and its connection with the formation of AA, we performed a molecular and genetic analysis of this polymorphism.

Results. The assumptions made were also proved by the results of mathematical analyses of differences between polymorphic loci of the TNF α (G-308A) gene in the studied groups.

Statistically insignificant differences were found between the frequencies of alleles and genotypes of the TNF α (G-308A) polymorphism in the main and control groups, amounting to less than one for the mutant A allele (5.2% vs. 5.6%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.9$; $RR = 1.0$; $CI: 0.45-2.22$; $OR = 0.9$; $CI: 0.38 - 2.3$), with a risk of developing the disease equal to 1.1 (OR) – for the main genotype (89.5% vs. 88.8%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.9$; $RR = 1.0$; $CI: 0.37-2.75$; $OR = 1.1$; $CI: 0.43-2.75$) and less than one for the G/A heterozygote (10.5% vs. 11.2%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.9$; $RR = 0.9$; $DI: 0.34-2.54$; $OR = 0.9$; $DI: 0.36-2.35$)

According to the polymorphic TNF α gene (G-308A), no statistically significant differences were found in the frequencies of allelic and genotypic variants between groups of patients with mild AA and healthy patients. The proof of this was the absence of significant differences among carriers of the mutant A allele (3.1% vs. 5.6%; $\chi^2 = 0.3$; $P = 0.6$; $RR = 1.0$; $DI: 0.69-1.4$; $OR = 0.5$; $DI: 0.07-4.22$), the main G|G homozygote (93.8% vs. 88.8%; $\chi^2 = 0.4$; $P = 0.6$; $RR = 1.1$; $DI: 0.02-46.7$; $OR = 1.9$; $DI: 0.24-15.3$) and the heterozygote G/A (6.3% vs. 11.2%; $\chi^2 = 0.4$; $P = 0.6$; $RR = 0.6$; $DI: 0.01-4.6$; $OR = 0.5$; $DI: 0.07-4.25$)

A similar analysis between groups of patients with severe AA and healthy controls confirmed the absence of statistically significant differences among carriers of polymorphic TNF α (G-308A) gene loci: attenuated A allele (5.4% vs. 5.6%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.98$; $RR = 1.0$; $CI: 0.51-1.94$; $OR = 0.5$; $DI: 0.33-2.87$), the main homozygote G/G (89.1% vs. 88.8%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.95$; $RR = 1.0$; $DI: 0.22-4.53$; $OR = 1.0$; $CI: 0.34-3.18$) and G/A heterozygotes (6.3% vs. 11.2%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; $P = 0.95$;

RR=1.0; CI: 0.21-4.37; OR=1.0; DI: 0.31-2.96). This means that the polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (G-308A) do not have an independent role in the formation of severe AA.

In the structure of the TNF α polymorphic gene (G-308A), a two-way comparative analysis between groups of patients with superheavy AA and healthy ones allowed us to determine the absence of statistically significant differences in the frequencies of allelic and genotypic variants. Thus, among patients, the frequency of the mutant allele A (6.3% vs. 5.6%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=1.0; DI: 0.58-1.75; OR=1.1; CI: 0.3-4.18) and heterozygous genotype G/A (12.5% vs. 11.2%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=1.1; CI: 0.14-9.14; OR=1.1; CI: 0.29-4.41) turned out to be slightly more than one, and the difference between the studied groups in the frequency of the main homozygote G/G did not even reach one (87.5% vs. 88.8%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=1.0; CI: 0.12-8.1; OR=1.9; DI: 0.23-3.46) and heterozygous. The results obtained serve as evidence of the absence of an independent relationship between polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (G-308A) and an increased risk of formation of the superheavy form of AA.

Analyzing the significance of differences in the frequencies of polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (G-308A) in a group of patients with mild AA compared with severe and superheavy forms of AA, there were significant differences in the carriage of the mutant A allele (3.1% vs. 5.4%; $\chi^2 = 0.3$; P=0.6; RR=1.0; DI: 0.47 - 2.03; OR=0.6; DI: 0.06-4.86 and 3.1% vs. 6.3%; $\chi^2 = 0.4$; P=0.6; RR=1.0; DI: 0.3-3.11; OR=0.5; DI: 0.05-4.66), the main genotype is G/G (93.8% vs. 89.1%; $\chi^2 = 0.3$; P=0.6; RR=1.1; DI: 0.03-38.79; OR=1.8; DI: 0.2-16.49 and 93.8% vs. 87.5%; $\chi^2 = 0.4$; P=0.6; RR=1.1; DI: 0.04-32.48; OR=2.1; DI: 0.21-21.68) and heterozygous G/A (6.3% vs. 10.9%; $\chi^2 = 0.3$; P=0.6; RR=0.6; DI: 0.02- 21.2; OR=0.5; DI: 0.06-4.93 and 6.3% vs. 12.5%; $\chi^2 = 0.4$; P=0.6; RR=0.5; DI: 0.02-15.16; OR=0.5; DI: 0.05-4.72) was not detected.

Along with this, comparing the degree of differences in the frequencies of polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (G-308A) between severe and superheavy forms of AA, there were significant differences in the carriage of the mutant A allele (5.4% vs. 6.3%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=1.0; CI: 0.16-6.08; OR=0.9; CI: 0.2-3.77), the main genotype G/G (89.1% vs. 87.5%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=1.0; CI: 0.34-3.09; OR=1.2; DI: 0.26-5.38) and heterozygous G/A (10.9% vs. 12.5%; $\chi^2 < 3.84$; P=0.9; RR=0.9; DI: 0.29- 2.63; OR=0.9; DI: 0.19-3.92) has also not been established.

Conclusion: The results obtained serve as evidence of the absence of an independent relationship between polymorphic loci of the TNF α gene (G-308A) and an increased risk of AA formation and its severe course in Uzbekistan.

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